

WP2 – Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Roadmap on tools for technical & administrative issues

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	2: Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors
Deliverable	Deliverable 2.2: Roadmap on tools for technical & administrative issues.
Date of report	10/06/2025
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2 Context- The DigitAF project

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Participatory research approach is key to engage with actors involved in the development of agroforestry and to unlock synergies among stakeholder to facilitate the implementation of innovations. In this preliminary action of the project, our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs and expectation, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisors playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This deliverable is found in the context of the DigitAF Work Package (WP) 2, which deals with optimising agroforestry design and management and tools for practitioners and farm advisors (WP2). More specifically, it is in the context of task 2.1: dealing with technical, administrative and financial aspects of installing and managing agroforestry.

Specifically, Deliverable 2.2 present an overview of the results obtained thanks to the survey applied to the Living Labs during the first two years of the project. In Deliverable 2.1 the structure of the survey performed was presented and extensively explained. In the current Deliverable report, particularly in section 3, we will focus on its results.

In section 4, we will present some examples of technical solutions adopted by at least three countries (Belgium-Flanders, Germany, and Italy) to overcome technical problems linked to agroforestry management. Particularly, these examples represent good-practice and pilot testing that can serve as examples to other farmers willing to adopt agroforestry. Therefore, the target-audience of section 4 are mainly farmers and consequently, the report will be short and explicative with figures.

In section 5, available tools that address technical issues will be presented and shortly described; a decision tree is proposed to help farmers/advisor in the selection of the suitable tool to address their technical issues.

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Finally, in section 6, an overview of the administrative issues related to agroforestry implementation will be shortly presented. The focus will be on at least three regions of Europe (Germany-Brandenburg, Belgium-Flanders, and Italy-Tuscany).

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3 Overview of farm-technical, labour-related and administrative challenges faced by agroforestry farmers

The survey form presented in D2.1 was shared among the six Living Labs (Belgium-Netherlands, Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Italy, and United Kingdom) and administered to the stakeholders, which included: academics, farm advisors, farmers and landowners, policy maker and others. A total of 92 surveys was conducted. In Tranchina et al. (2024) further details on survey methodology and an in-depth analysis of the results is presented. In this section a brief overview of only the technical and administrative issues will be presented.

Stakeholders recognised as main limiting factors to the adoption of agroforestry the following issues: (i) the fear of losing CAP payments if the number of tree/ha is increased, (ii) the administrative burden linked with agroforestry implementation, (iii) lack of technical knowledge by workers, and (iv) the lack of knowledge of tree management on farmland. Other technical factors that limit agroforestry adoption are: (i) the changes in agroforestry-mechanical operations, (ii) lack of available resources regarding agroforestry management, (iii) absence of network of knowledge regarding technical issues related to agroforestry systems, and the increased complexity of agroforestry systems.

Focusing on agricultural operations, stakeholders perceived (i) crop harvesting operations, (ii) crop species selection, and (iii) soil tillage practice as more complex to performed in an agroforestry system compared to a conventional system. Beyond these main obstacles, stakeholders highlighted many other issues related to agroforestry system management expressing their needs in receiving support, from advisors/networks/websites/digital tools, on several aspects. For example, they need technical advice and support on crop, plant, and tree selection based on local agro-climatic and soil conditions. In addition, they express their necessity in using tools for optimal area design and harvesting efficiency. On the other hand, agroforestry uptake is also limited by administrative and policy-related obstacles that include: (i) policy and legal constrains, (ii) ignorance of local administration, (iii) lack of political support, (iv) policy issues regarding harvesting and tenancy, (v) complex application for CAP funds, (vi) challenges in parcel registration combined with other administrative tasks, (vii) potential replanting obligations, and (viii) the perception that local support rules do not encourage agroforestry systems.

Within this section, an analysis of the technical and administrative issues ranked by the stakeholders according to the country will be performed. The aim is to highlight if there are any differences regarding the perceived technical and administrative issues depending on the climatic area and location.

In Table 1, survey results regarding the section 4.15 of TECHNICAL potential obstacles are presented. Overall, stakeholders did not perceive the technical problems as Extremely problematic as the overall average is equal to 1.9, so Problematic. The values range from 1.3 (Slightly problematic) to 2.2 (Problematic) according to the country; the lower value was given by Finnish stakeholders (1.3) and the highest values given by the Italian stakeholders (2.2). In respect to the practices, the values range from 1.3 (Slightly problematic) to 2.6 (Problematic) with the lowest value given to “Availability

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of species adequate to be grown in AF systems (cereals, fodder crops) (1.3) and the highest value given to *“Water provision of young trees”* (2.6).

Table 2 presents survey results regarding section 4.16 about differences in the operations performed in agroforestry systems compared to conventional ones. Overall, stakeholders perceived as more complicated the operations performed in agroforestry systems compared to conventional system as the overall average is 2.2. There are not any great differences between the values assigned according to the country as the values range from 2.0 to 2.3 with the lower value given by Belgian, Finnish, Italian, and Dutch stakeholders (2.0) and the highest values given by the Czechs stakeholders (2.3). In respect to the operations, the values range from 1.8 (Less complicated/More complicated) to 2.3 (More complicated) with the lowest value given to *“Reduction in pesticide use”* (1.8) and the highest value given to *“Crop species selection”* (2.3).

In Table 3, survey results regarding the section 4.19 of ADMINISTRATIVE potential obstacles are presented. Overall, stakeholders did not perceive the technical problems as Extremely problematic as the overall average is equal to 1.7, so Problematic. The values range from 1.2 (Slightly problematic) to 2.3 (Problematic) according to the country; the lower value was given by Finnish stakeholders (1.2) while the highest values given by the Belgian stakeholders (2.3). In respect to the administrative potential obstacle, the values range from 0.8 (Slightly problematic) to 2.1 (Problematic) with the lowest value given to *“Issues related to food safety”* (0.8) and the highest value given to *“Administrative burden when implementing AF systems”* (2.1).

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Table 1. Summary of the values given to potential TECHNICAL obstacles to the application of agroforestry practices perceived by the stakeholders according to the country. From 0 to 4: 0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant.

Country	Belgium	Czech Republic	Finland	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	United Kingdom	Average
Number of respondents	7	29	8	12	11	14	8	89
Potential obstacle								
Increased complexity of AF systems	1.7	1.5	1.6	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.1	1.7
Level of knowledge regarding the management of trees on farmland	1.7	2.1	1.1	2.3	2.1	2.1	2.5	1.7
Availability of resources regarding the management of AF systems	2.0	1.7	1.5	1.9	1.9	2.2	2.3	2.0
Availability of species adequate to be grown in AF systems (cereals, fodder crops)	1.3	1.0	0.8	1.4	2.1	0.9	1.3	1.3
Interaction with livestock	2.0	1.4	0.8	1.3	1.7	0.8	2.0	2.0
Effect on the yields of the main crop	1.7	1.5	1.3	1.6	2.7	1.2	1.9	1.7
Changes in agro-mechanical operations	2.4	1.7	1.6	2.1	2.7	2.0	1.9	2.4
Presence of a network of knowledge regarding technical issues related to AF systems	1.6	1.7	1.6	2.2	2.3	1.4	2.6	1.6
Harvesting fruits/ nuts from the trees	2.6	1.1	1.5	1.8	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.6
Pruning of the trees	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.9	2.0	1.2	1.1	1.4
Technical knowledge of agricultural workers (employees)	2.1	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.9	1.8	2.8	2.1
Water provision of young trees	2.6	1.5	0.6	2.6	2.4	1.5	2.1	2.6
Average	1.9	1.5	1.3	1.9	2.2	1.6	2.0	1.9

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Table 2. Summary of the values given to potential the perceived level of difficulties in implementing some operation in an agroforestry system compared to a conventional one. Values given by the by the stakeholders according to the country. From 1 to 3: 1 -Less complicated; 2- More complicated; 3- Equally complicated.

Country	Belgium	Czech Republic	Finland	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	United Kingdom	Average
Number of respondents	7	25	8	12	11	14	8	85
Operation								
Management of weeds	2.0	2.2	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
Management of pests/diseases	1.7	2.5	1.5	1.9	1.4	1.6	1.9	1.9
Harvesting operations	2.1	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.2	2.0	2.1	2.1
Reduction in pesticide use	1.6	2.1	1.8	2.0	1.6	1.3	2.0	1.8
Soil tillage practices	2.1	2.2	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.4	2.2
Fertilization plan	2.6	2.4	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	1.9	2.2
Crop species selection	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.3
Average	2.0	2.3	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.1	2.1

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Table 3. Summary of the values given to potential ADMINISTRATIVE issues to the application of agroforestry practices perceived by the stakeholders according to the country. From 0 to 4: 0- Not problematic at all; 1- Slightly problematic; 2- Problematic; 3- Very problematic; 4- Extremely problematic; X - Not relevant

Country	Belgium	Czech Republic	Finland	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	United Kingdom	Average
Number of respondents	7	29	8	11	11	14	8	88
Potential obstacle								
Administrative burden when implementing AF systems	2.6	2.0	1.9	2.5	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.1
Issues related to accountancy	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.3	1.4	1.3
Issues related to land ownership	3.3	1.9	0.9	2.1	2.1	1.3	2.0	1.9
Issues related to permits for planting trees	2.1	1.8	0.5	2.1	1.5	1.9	2.1	1.7
Issues related to permits for removing trees	2.7	1.6	0.8	2.5	2.5	1.9	2.3	1.9
Issues related to food safety	1.3	0.7	0.9	0.8	1.1	0.6	0.3	0.8
Issues related to permits for agroforestry-related infrastructure	2.1	1.2	1.0	2.2	2.3	1.0	0.8	1.5
Entity of support of Common Agricultural Policy measures	2.4	2.5	2.3	1.5	2.8	1.1	0.8	2.0
Average	2.3	1.6	1.2	1.9	2.0	1.4	1.4	1.7

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Overall Finnish stakeholders perceived less obstacles in implementing AF as they assigned the lower values both in the TECHNICAL (Table 1) and ADMINISTRATIVE (Table 3) issues; while in the differences in the operations, on average they were perceived as more complicated. Whereas in Italy, stakeholders assigned high values to the TECHNICAL potential obstacles (Table 3) and for the ADMINISTRATIVE obstacles, Italy is the second country following Belgium. Italian stakeholders perceived as Extremely problematic (average near to 3) the: (i) “*Effect on the yields of the main crop*” (2.7); (ii) “*Changes in agro-mechanical operations*” (2.7); and (iii) “*Technical knowledge of agricultural workers (employees)*” (2.9). These potential technical obstacles were not perceived as extremely problematic from the other LL stakeholders as their average was closer to 2 (Problematic) except for Belgian stakeholders which assign 2.4 to “*Changes in agro-mechanical operations*” and UK stakeholders which assign 2.8 to “*Technical knowledge of agricultural workers (employees)*”. UK stakeholders perceived also as Extremely problematic (i) the “*Presence of a network of knowledge regarding technical issues related to AF systems*” (2.6) and (ii) the “*Level of knowledge regarding the management of trees on farmland*”. Belgian stakeholders perceived also as Extremely problematic (i) the “*Harvesting fruits/ nuts from the trees*” (2.6) and (ii) the “*Water provision of young trees*” (2.6).

Interestingly, stakeholders perceived as Slightly problematic / Problematic the “*Availability of species adequate to be grown in AF systems (cereals, fodder crops)*” (1.3); but when it comes to the “*Crop species selection*”, the operation is perceived as More complicated compared to other operations (2.3). These results might indicate that species are present, but stakeholders required further knowledge during the selection process for their use in the AF system. The “*Soil tillage practices*” and the “*Fertilization plan*” were also perceived as more complicated operations in respect to the management of diseases and pests.

Belgium assigned the highest values to ADMINISTRATIVE issues compared to other country; this is linked with “*Issues related to land ownership*” that scored 3.3 (Very problematic / Extremely problematic). A brief overview of this issues will be described in section 7. Excluding these issues, perceived administrative issues are below 3 and in line with the values given by the other countries.

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4 Pilot-testing of novel techniques and machinery

Within this section, results of pilot testing and demonstration activities will be presented in 9 factsheets. The target-audience of the factsheet are farmers and farm advisors; therefore, they will be concise, direct and rich in figures. The aim is to create contents to share the developed knowledge regarding critical issues observed in agroforestry systems and the related solution employed to overcome them.

List of the factsheets:

1. Nut harvesting: machinery demos in Flanders (BE)
2. Weed suppression near tree rows by buffer strips of Miscanthus on an Arable field in Flanders (BE)
3. Implementation of swales in erosion-prone areas (BE)
4. Implementation of an agrosilvopastoral systems in Mediterranean plain area: limits and opportunities (IT)
5. Nutritional determination of leaves and stems on different poplar's clones in an innovative Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral system (IT)
6. Management of drainage ditches in an agrosilvopastoral systems: single-side ditcher (IT)
7. Experiences, advantages and disadvantages of machineries for the establishment, maintenance and re-cultivation of AFS (DE)
8. Available machineries for fruit and nut harvesting in AFS (DE)
9. Available machineries for timber harvesting in AFS (DE)

These topics were chosen to answer the needs expressed by farmers during the survey (see previous section), while being complementary with existing factsheets for farmers. Indeed, during previous projects, other materials for farmers and/or researchers were collected and created, particularly during the AGFORWARD project (FP7, GA 613520), the AFINET project (H2020, GA 727872) and AGROMIX project (H2020, GA 862993).

AGFORWARD (<https://www.agforward.eu/>)

- Innovation leaflets: <https://agforward.eu/Innovation-leaflets.html>
- Best practice leaflets: <https://agforward.eu/best-practices-leaflets.html>

AFINET (<https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/it/afinet>)

- Technical articles: <https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet/materials/technical-articles>
- Factsheets: <https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet/materials/factsheet>
- Innovation tutorials: <https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet/materials/innovation-tutorials>
- Handbook: <https://agroforestrynet.eu/>

AGROMIX (<https://agromixproject.eu/>)

- Knowledge hub: <https://agromixproject.eu/knowledge-hub/>
- Pilot projects and trial sites: <https://agromixproject.eu/in-the-field/>

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Nut harvesting: Machinery demos in Flanders (BE)

Summary: This factsheet presents the feedback obtained after the demonstration of machineries for nut harvesting held in Flanders.

Problem to solve: Both walnut (*Juglans regia*) and hazel (*Corylus avellana*) are considered valuable species for integration in agroforestry systems. One of their main advantages is the production of marketable nuts. However, the question often arises how these nuts can efficiently be harvested.

Solution: To meet this demand, in an earlier project (VLAIO 2020-2024), ILVO made an inventory of suitable machinery for nut harvesting and developed a factsheet (in Dutch) and basic decision support tool (MIMOSA) for machinery selection; in section 5 a description of the decision support tool MIMOSA is presented. Also, as part of DigitAF activities, ILVO organized/participated in two demo events. Firstly, ILVO participated in the Werktuigendagen 2023. This is a biannual two-day event where agricultural machinery of all sorts is demonstrated. Amongst the more than 50 000 visitors are both professional farmers and private individuals. Secondly, a pilot-testing period followed by a demo-session with two Bag-a-nut harvesters was organized, aimed at nut-harvesting in small scale farm operations.

Werktuigendagen 2023

ILVO participated in the Werktuigendagen 2023 through the organization of (amongst others activities) an outdoor stand focussing on mechanization in agroforestry systems (Fig. 1). Besides machinery used for planting and pruning trees and hedges, two machines used for the harvest of walnuts and hazelnuts were shown. Both machines shown are mainly used by medium to large farm enterprises.

Fig. 1 Outdoor stand of ILVO at the Werktuigendagen 2023 with demonstration of the R06 and a tree shaker (amongst others)

Firstly, a tree shaker was provided by [Lerouge Natuurlijk](#). Several types of tree shakers exist, but the principle remains the same (Fig. 2). They are generally powered by a tractor which by gripping the trunk or through connection of a belt causes an intense shaking of the tree trunk. As a result, the nuts let loose of the branches and fall, whereby they are caught and/or collected. Secondly, an R06 harvester ([AMB Rousset](#), Fig. 2) provided by [VELD4](#) was shown. This machine is used for picking

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and sorting fallen nuts (and/or fruits) of the ground. The R06 is one of the smaller pickers in the assortment of AMB Rousset but still considered suitable for harvesting up to 5 hectares of nut trees.

Fig. 2. Demonstrated nut harvesting machines. Left: R06 (AMB Rousset). Right: tree shaker.

Bag-a-nut Pilot testing and demo

A second demo was organized at the agroforestry site with hazelnut trees and poultry of ILVO. Two nut collecting machines developed by Bag-a-nut were first tested and subsequently demonstrated to a group of 10 relevant stakeholders including mainly nut producers but also tree nurseries: the 18" Pick up harvester and the 21" Pro Push harvester (Fig. 3). The machines were provided by *Morphing creativity bvba*. Both machines are oriented at private individuals or small-scale professional operations. They are pushed around while nuts are picked by the brush and collected in the container on the machine. The pick-up harvester is considered the entry-level apparatus, whereas the Pro Push harvester is more suitable for heavy use.

Fig. 3. Left: Bag-a-nut 18" Pick up harvester. Right: Bag-a-nut 21" Pro Push harvester.

Interested farmers were invited for a live demonstration of both tools with explanation by the importer and possibility of testing (Fig. 4). In addition, a trial was conducted whereby known amounts of hazelnuts were spread out on three types of grassland: i) a zone of the agroforestry field which is intensively used by the poultry, resulting in a lot of bumps and holes, ii) moderately used zone of the agroforestry field and iii) well maintained grassland with short grass and without any bumps or holes. The nuts were collected by both harvesters to evaluate and compare their speed of working, efficiency and efficacy. Both apparatuses worked very well in well maintained grassland, in particular the Pro Push (Table 4).

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Table 1. Comparison of nut harvesting efficacy.

	Nut harvesting efficacy (% of nuts recollected)	
	21" Pro Push	18" Pick up
Agroforestry intensively used	0.66	0.58
Agroforestry moderately used	0.77	0.78
Well maintained grassland	0.94	0.84

Efficiency lowered in the agroforestry system, though was still fairly high in the zone which was only moderately frequented by the poultry. Though 100% efficacy was never reached, the tools aid in harvesting most of the nuts in a very limited time span when compared to e.g. hand-picking.

Fig. 4. Left: trial to assess the performance of both Bag-a-nut harvesters. Right: demo with explanation and possibility for testing.

Advantages and disadvantages of the demonstrated machinery were discussed in detail for each type of apparatus during the demo-events. These are however strongly dependent on the type of farming enterprise and the field to be harvested. However, some general positive and negative points are mentioned below and are described in more detail in the fact sheet “Oogst van noten: welke methodes en machines?” (“harvest of nuts: which methods and machinery”).

Advantages

- Tree shaking machines allow the harvest of large quantities of nuts at once (up to 95%).
- Use of tree nets is more suitable for rough terrain
- Bag-a-nut harvester are relatively cheap and can considerably increase speed of picking fallen nuts when compared to manual picking

Disadvantages

- Most machines that pick fallen nuts from the ground require a flat and well-maintained soil surface.
- Although no consensus exists, tree shaking machines are assumed to potentially damage (fine) tree roots and/or tree bark.
- Use of tree nets is labor-intensive.

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Weed suppression near tree rows by buffer strips of *Miscanthus* on an Arable field in Flanders (BE)

Summary: this factsheet explores the issues related to management of tree strips. The content of the factsheet was developed by ILVO based on literature and complemented with field observations and practitioners' experience.

Problem to solve: Proper management of (the field zone near) tree strips is a technical issue frequently raised by practitioners, amongst others in terms of reducing the risk of potential weed proliferation from the (often more extensive) strips into the field.

Solution: In the context of the DigitAF project, based upon the survey outcomes as well as participatory suggestions from our farmers' network, we took some next steps in pilot testing tree strip management techniques, including the miscanthus pilot testing described in this paragraph. To counter the potentially increased weed pressure in arable alley cropping fields near the tree rows, a trial was set up in which strips of *Miscanthus* spp. were established as a buffer between the tree rows and the neighbouring arable zone (Fig. 5). Below, the rationale and implementation of the strips is discussed. To fully utilise the ecological potential of the tree strips in agroforestry systems, organic management without the use of herbicides is often advised. In some cases, this may even be mandatory, as is the case in Flanders to obtain the subsidy for tree strip maintenance. However, this may create issues with increased weed pressure in the cropping zone because of colonization from the tree strips.

Fig. 6. Left: weed pressure in the arable zone because of organic tree strip management. Right: recently established tree strips where buffer cropping strips will be implemented.

This was also encountered by a conventional arable agroforestry farmer in Flanders (Belgium). Therefore, to avoid this problem on a newly established silvoarable alley cropping field with four walnut rows (*Juglans regia*), cropping strips adjacent to and parallel with the tree strips were established to create a buffer between the tree rows and the arable zone. The field is in the South of Flanders and is characterised by a loamy soil with good moisture conditions. Initially, different types of crops were considered: *Miscanthus sinensis*, a wildflower mixture, hemp (*Cannabis sativa*), *Sorghum bicolor* and a grass-clover mixture. Whereas at first a combination of these crops was foreseen, in the end the farmer decided to border all four tree rows on both sides with miscanthus. The latter is characterised by a generally successful propagation and establishment. In addition, the fast growth and dense vegetation structure provides multiple benefits such as efficient weed sup-

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pression and the provision of cover for game species and other wildlife, while producing marketable biomass.

Fig. 7. Propagation of miscanthus is fairly easy by subdividing root systems.

Though labour-intensive, both propagation (Fig. 7) and planting were done manually. The first strips were planted in the early spring of 2023 by the farmer and ILVO. The other strips were planted in the following years by the farmer. Width of the strips varied between two and three meters. Planting distances equalled 1m x 1m. Two years after planting, the miscanthus had established well with only very limited mortality (Fig. 8).

Fig 8. Tree strips approximately two years after plantation of the miscanthus

Up till present, no maintenance of the miscanthus is needed and its presence does not hamper the cultivation of the neighbouring cropping alleys. Although the used planting differences are as standard, weed suppression after two years is still limited. This is expected to increase in the years to come when the miscanthus becomes more dominant. A similar demo-field with miscanthus of two years age at Praktijkpunt Landbouw Vlaams-Brabant is shown below (Fig. 9). This illustrates differences in rate of development which can amongst others be related to environmental and/or planting conditions, size and quality of the planting material, management of the (competing) vegetation in the strip during the establishment phase.

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Fig. 9. Example of a similar demo system at *Praktijkpunt Landbouw Vlaams-Brabant (Belgium)*. Picture below shows the situation two years after installing the *Miscanthus*.

- **Other pilot tests and demos with tree strip management**

Besides these pilot tests with buffer strips of *Miscanthus*, at the ILVO experimental fields we have a comparative test with strip mowing regime ongoing (since 2023). In this pilot test, three tree strips sown with a dense mixture of tall fescue, white clover and lucerne are subject to different mowing regimes and shifts in species composition and flowering times are monitored. The test is briefly shown in [this demo video](#), but the full results are not yet available and will be incorporated in a later phase in the updated factsheet (see section 6).

Advantages: the use of both ways of tree strip management may constitute an environmentally friendly way to combat weed colonization of the field through avoiding herbicide use and by creating semi-permanent habitat. Moreover, additional harvestable produce and/or income is realised. Once established, relatively limited time and labour input is needed for maintenance.

Disadvantages: The cultivation of new crops or use of new cropping techniques may require additional knowledge of the farmer. In addition, the creation of *miscanthus* crops may cause administrative complexities (e.g. LPIS)

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Implementation of swales in erosion-prone areas (BE)

Summary: In Flanders, multiple fields are confronted with excess runoff, leading to poor hydrology and water stocks, erosion and consecutive negative effects at the landscape scale (e.g. downstream flooding). The installation of swales in agricultural fields may be an interesting technique to simultaneously counter these issues without compromising agricultural productivity.

Problem to solve: As a result of recent drought periods and extreme weather-events leading to erosion and flooding, water management is receiving increasing attention in Flanders. The need to reduce runoff and enhance water stocks at field level is increasingly being recognized. In particular on slopy fields where these effects may be further aggravated.

Solution: An interesting approach may be the use of swales, whether or not combined with agroforestry (Fig. 11). A swale consists of a ditch, constructed on a sloping plot in combination with an adjacent verge downhill. These structures are constructed parallel to the contour lines. The verge is usually sown or planted with grasses, herbs or vegetables to obtain an effective ground cover and/or planted with perennial woody plants.

Fig 11. Arable field with recently constructed swales in Heuvelland. Source: Bert Reubens

When runoff reaches the swales, it is collected in the ditches, where it can infiltrate or is diverted to small reservoirs along the swale. The aim here is multiple:

- i) Increasing water storage in the plot, for example to improve the growing conditions for cultivated crops
- ii) Preventing soil erosion and the washing away of fertile soil
- iii) Preventing or reducing problems caused by excess water in areas situated downslope.
- iv) Providing additional system services (e.g. C-storage) and increasing biodiversity

The best time to install swales is during periods of low rainfall in spring or autumn. The dimensions of the swales and the distances between them must be calculated based on the amount of water that one wants to be able to collect and the infiltration capacity of the soil (Fig. 12). No soil is added or removed during installation. In principle, the swales are always placed according to the contour lines. An A-frame or laser can be used to set out the swales according to the contour lines, or a surveyor can be called in. It may be useful to provide overflow structures in case the runoff water exceeds the capacity of the swale. When installing the swale, compaction of the soil must be avoided as much as possible. Experience shows that a 3-ton crawler crane is usually sufficient to carry out

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the work. To prevent erosion, the bare soil should be sown as soon as possible after the excavation works, for example with water-resistant grasses (reed fescue, timothy grass) or green manures. Mulch can be applied in the ditches if necessary to enhance SOC.

Fig 12. Construction of swales using laser and 3T crane. Source: Christel Cornelissen

Advantages: The installation of swales is an environmentally friendly measure that can enhance the hydrology at both the field and the landscape scale. Given proper design and management, swales may simultaneously lead to increased SOC, biodiversity and landscape values. Finally, swales lend themselves to multi-functional economic use too, e.g. by cultivation specific crops on the area used for the verges.

Disadvantages: A significant investment of time for the design and establishment of the swales should be considered. The elevation lines should be meticulously followed to ascertain good functioning of the swale. This may result in cropping zones with varying width which may complicate agricultural activities, in particular when heavily mechanized farming methods are used. The installation of swales may be subject to governmental restrictions and permits, which in some cases may be challenging to obtain.

Note: In spite of the historically limited occurrence of such systems in Flanders (and Belgium), recently, several fields have been established. ILVO assisted in the design of these systems and the first evaluation after their establishment through the ongoing project [AFaktive](#).

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Implementation of an agrosilvopastoral system in Mediterranean plain area: limits and opportunities. The case-study of DIGITAF LTE

Summary: This factsheet presents the limits and opportunities of implementing an agroforestry system in a Mediterranean plain. Thanks to the DIGITAF project, a long-term experiment (LTE) was established: specifically, an agrosilvopastoral system with several tree species was planted in 2024 at the experimental farm of the University of Pisa. The aim is to use this site as a pilot study to support other farmers in adopting similar systems.

Problem to solve: Before the Green Revolution, trees in agricultural fields were widespread across Tuscany. Tree rows along field edges provided several benefits, such as serving as windbreaks, reducing nutrient leaching, and supplying wood and fodder for animals. Today, however, farmers are often sceptical about adopting agroforestry systems due to the perceived reduction in crop yields, technical challenges, and administrative issues. The goal of this pilot project was to implement an agrosilvopastoral system in an arable field to assess its limits and opportunities, ultimately providing practical advice to facilitate the wider adoption of agroforestry practices by farmers.

Solution: Figure 13 shows an aerial view of the trial site. The experiment covers 9 hectares of reclaimed land, with soil texture clay-loam. In March 2024, approximately 1,000 one-year-old trees and shrubs were planted across ten rows. A planting scheme is shown in Figure 13. The design includes one control plot (no trees) and three different tree row spacings: 30, 90, and 270 meters.

Additionally, a sub-irrigation system will be installed for the herbaceous crop, with three watering levels: 0%, 50%, and 100% of the crop's water requirements. Each tree row distance (0, 30, 90, and 270 meters) will be tested with the three irrigation levels.

The tree row species include a mix of tall trees and shrubs, specifically: white poplar (*Populus alba* L.), Spanish broom (*Spartium junceum* L.), field maple (*Acer campestre* L.), alder buckthorn (*Frangula alnus* Mill.), white mulberry (*Morus alba* L.), hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna* Jacq.), crab apple (*Malus sylvestris* (L.) Mill.), common broom (*Cytisus scoparius* (L.) Link), and black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.).

In the herbaceous layer, a mixed temporary grassland will be established.

Advantages: Agrosilvopastoral systems are productive systems based on agroforestry practices that combine tree and shrub species with one or more agricultural crops (annual or perennial), pastures, or permanent meadows, with the possible integration of livestock. Specifically, in agrosilvopastoral systems:

1. Shrub species or tree branches can be consumed directly by animals or cut for forage.
2. Tall tree species provide shade for grazing animals, reducing heat stress.
3. Shading can enhance the protein content of forage species adjacent to tree-shrub rows.
4. Tree rows help increase carbon storage and support biodiversity conservation.

Disadvantages: One-year-old plants were initially chosen due to their lower cost; however, without adequate irrigation and weeding management, the survival rate after the first year was around 50%

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(Fig. 14). In March 2025, dead plants were replaced with two-year-old plants (Fig. 15). Irrigation activities are still ongoing.

It is strongly recommended to use older plants, despite their higher initial cost, as they offer a much higher survival rate, eliminating the need for costly replacements after the first year.

Expected results: Once the tree and shrub species are sufficiently developed, the grassland will be grazed by a local beef cattle breed (Mucco Pisano) under a rational grazing management scheme. The shrubs and tree branches will serve as supplementary feed for the cattle during the summer months, contributing to improved self-sufficiency of the farm.

Fig. 13. Aerial view of the experimental field and experimental scheme of the long-term experiment

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Fig. 14. Planting of plants during the first year

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Fig. 15. Re-planting of dead plants during the second year

Nutritional determination of leaves and stems on different poplar's clones in an innovative Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral System (IT)

Summary: This factsheet presents the results of a trial conducted within the DIGITAF project which investigate the use of poplar leaves and stems as a sustainable forage source in Mediterranean agrosilvopastoral systems. Results of analysis for nutritive values determination of fresh and ensiled poplar leaves are presented.

Problem to solve: During the summer, Mediterranean regions face limited water availability due to high temperatures, which significantly restricts pasture production for ruminants (Fig. 16). As a result, there is an increasing need to identify sustainable, on-farm forage sources to reduce reliance on market purchases. In this context, poplar emerges as a promising solution due its capacity to catch water in the deeper soil layers and its fast growth. These characteristics make poplar well-suited to dry summer conditions. Moreover, poplar trees offer multiple benefits, including fresh forage, timber, carbon sequestration, and shade for grazing animals. The system is currently being tested on two farms in southern Tuscany (Fig. 17), where poplar trees are integrated with coppiced clones for forage production. The nutritive values of fresh and ensiled poplar leaves and stems (Fig. 18) were analysed according to the nutritional recommendations of the Cornell Net Carbohydrate and Protein System (CNCPS) model (Table 5).

Fig. 16. Typical dry summer pasture in Southern Tuscany, middle of June 2024

Fig. 17. Layout of poplar clones, with the alternation of one tall poplar for shading and three coppiced poplars for forage production.

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Advantages: The integration of poplar-based agroforestry systems enhances farm resilience in multiple ways. Firstly, it ensures the availability of fresh forage during the summer months, when herbaceous pastures are typically scarce. The biomass harvested from coppiced poplars can also be stored as silage for winter feeding, reducing the need for external forage purchases and increasing the farm's self-sufficiency.

In addition to its role as a forage source, poplar provides valuable shade in grazing areas, helping to mitigate heat stress in livestock during hot periods. Poplar trees can also be managed for timber production, offering farmers an opportunity to diversify their income sources. Moreover, the system contributes to climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration in tree biomass and soils, with the potential to generate additional income via carbon credit trading. Altogether, this multifunctional approach supports greater sustainability, economic stability, and environmental resilience in Mediterranean farming system.

Disadvantages: The system presents some practical limitations. One of the main challenges is the lack of efficient and scalable methods for harvesting the forage component, particularly in small or uneven plots. Without appropriate mechanization or adapted management practices, this aspect could limit broader adoption by farmers. Moreover, to make timber production economically viable, it is essential to have a local wood-processing facility capable of purchasing and transforming the biomass. Another limitation that emerged from this study is the relatively low nutritional quality of poplar leaves, which contain less quantitative and quality protein compared to alfalfa hay, typically used in summer months.

Fig 18. Silage production

Table 5. Nutritive values of poplar leaves and steams of different clones and the silage after 40 days of ensiling. DM: dry matter; NDF: neutral detergent fibre; NDFom: neutral detergent fiber or-

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ganic matter; ADF: acid detergent fibre; ADLom: acid detergent lignin organic matter; CP: crude protein; NDICP: neutral detergent insoluble crude protein ; EE: ether extract.

Common name: Poplar

Scientific name: *Populus* spp.

Family: Salicaceae

Harvesting period: Summer 2024, from June to July

Location: Grosseto, Tuscany, Italy

Silage technique: 40 days

Clone		I214	Imola	JPT	Or-ion	Tucano	Mean	Sil-age
Dry matter								
% fresh biomass								
	Leaves	34.4	33.5	34.1	34.2	33.9	34	80.1
	Stems	32.5	34	29.7	31.7	33.8	32.3	
Chemical composition								
% DM								
NDF	Leaves	39.7	42.3	40.7	40.1	40.2	40.6	48.1
	Stems	57.0	60.4	61.9	59.3	57.5	59.2	
NDFom	Leaves	38.7	40.0	38.9	37.4	39.4	39.8	47.1
	Stems	55.7	59.4	60.7	58.0	56.1	57.9	
ADF	Leaves	31.0	34	34.1	32.3	33.4	32.9	33.1
	Stems	44.6	47.7	50.7	47.0	46.4	47.2	
ADLom	Leaves	12.5	14.5	16.1	15.1	13.5	14.3	11.3
	Stems	13.8	14.8	16.5	14.3	13.8	14.6	
CP	Leaves	12.5	12.1	11	11.5	13.7	12.1	8.1
	Stems	5.4	4.7	5	4.1	6.2	5.0	
NDICP	Leaves	8.0	8.3	7.8	8.0	9.7	8.3	6.6
	Stems	3.2	2.9	3.5	2.8	4.1	3.3	
EE	Leaves	2.3	3.6	2.4	1.9	1.5	2.3	2.6
	Stems	2.2	1.6	1.9	3.0	2.2	2.1	
Ash	Leaves	11.5	13.7	9.1	13	11.2	11.7	8.7
	Stems	9.2	8.5	5.9	9.1	7.9	8.1	

Management of drainage ditches in an agrosilvopastoral systems: single-side ditcher (IT)

Summary: this factsheet deal with the management of ditches along the tree rows. Characteristics and pictures of a single-side ditcher are presented.

Problem to solve: Creating ditches in an agroforestry system presents several challenges, mainly related to the presence of trees, the availability of space for machinery, and water management. Traditional machines may not be able to effectively address these issues.

Solution: Within the AGROMIX and DIGITAF projects, a single-side arm ditcher was acquired for the construction and definition of drainage ditches within the DIGITAF LTE trial-site, to support effective surface water management (Fig. 19).

The machine's digging speed is 20 meters per minute (m/min), which is equivalent to a digging capacity of 0.33 meters per second (m/s). This value reflects the operational efficiency of the machine in trenching, optimizing work time while maintaining precision and quality in drainage tasks. The ditcher has a working depth range of 55 to 77 cm, with a wall inclination of either 30° or 45°, enabling versatile digging and precise trench shaping based on the specific requirements of the field.

Advantages: Compared to non-arm bilateral ditchers, the single-arm configuration allows for greater flexibility, precise ditch profiling, and enhanced adaptability to irregular or sloped terrains. These features make it particularly suitable for use in Mediterranean agroforestry systems, where field conditions often require targeted and flexible ditching operations.

This solution allows to work in tight spaces. With its articulated arm, this machine can operate close to trees and crops without damaging them, ensuring precision and flexibility. Additionally, its ability to reach difficult areas without compromising soil stability or damaging roots makes it ideal for working in an agroforestry system.

Disadvantages: Due to the significant lateral load and offset working position, special attention must be paid to rollover risk. The ditcher requires a heavy-duty tractor weighing over 5,000 kg to ensure safe and stable operation, especially on sloping ground.

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Fig. 19. Single -die ditcher during field operation (a, b, c); drainage ditch after the operation (d)

Experiences, advantages and disadvantages of machinery for the establishment, maintenance and re-cultivation of agroforestry systems (DE)

Summary: This factsheet presents a selection of the machineries for the establishment and maintenance of AFS currently present on the market.

Problems to solve: Standard forestry machines can be used in the agroforestry sector, provided that their size and operation modes can be adapted to the agricultural conditions and their use makes sense economically. However, as agroforestry systems are often rather small-scale and complex in structure and the field layout differs, large machines from the forestry sector are often not suitable.

Solutions for planting: As farmers already have machines for soil cultivation, these are primarily planting machines for seedlings, rods, trees or shrubs. The machines differ in terms of automatic and manual planting, the number of trees or rows planted in one operation and their manoeuvrability (trailing systems, self-propelled), (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. A small tractor-attached earth auger with a wide diameter. Author: R. Weissheidinger.

Fig. 2. Compressed walls of planting holes should be avoided. Author: J. Günzel.

For the manual planting, suitable to smaller AFS with fruit and nut trees, a manual soil auger with a wider diameter is suitable, which loosens the soil in the planting hole area, e.g. the **heart-shaped soil auger** e.g. from German manufacturer, [Stihl](#). Due to its design, this auger works effectively and loosens the soil while drilling planting holes quickly and effortlessly. This is important to solve the problem of a compressed wall of the drilling hole, which makes it difficult for roots to penetrate the surrounding soil, thus prohibiting a proper root development and a stable foundation of the trees.

The agroforestry service company **LIGNOVIS** uses a semi-manual planting device especially suited for poplar rods of 1 to 2 m length, an attachable platform to a tractor (Fig. 3) or for cuttings (Fig. 4).

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Fig. 3. Planting platform for line planting of long rods from poplar and other fast-growing trees, 1.5 to 1.8 m length. Author: T. Köhn.

Fig. 4. The LignoPlanter-C from Lignovis plants more than 10 ha of cuttings per day. Author: M. Weitz.

The Swiss company [RhenusTEC GmbH](#) developed a machine for soil-friendly planting bed preparation specifically for AFS. Their **Tree Line Preparer TLP-80 S** is a mixture of cultivator and rotary tiller that loosens the soil to a depth of 45 cm, making it easy to plant trees. This machine can be used for planting nut and fruit trees, shrubs, hedges, timber trees, energy wood and for growing vegetables.

Solutions for maintenance: During the lifetime of a fruit or nut tree, regular training and, in the case of timber production, pruning is necessary. In AFS with fruit or nut trees, the understorey also needs maintenance. Tree training and limbing are usually carried out manually with a handsaw (< 5 cm diameter), however proper equipment and most essentially, professional training is necessary (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Manual tree training and limbing requires skills and a high level of personal safety equipment. Author: R. Hübner.

Fig. 6. Manual planting with a petrol driven auger. Author: M. Bärwolff.

Roller or share hoes, or harrows are suitable for understorey maintenance in SRC. It is particularly important to use them early on to contain accompanying vegetation, especially in the case of poplar cuttings. There exist also special devices for this, e.g. the **BP 2/4 understorey cultivator** from [LIPCO](#).

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In AFS with fruit or nut production, understorey care should be particularly gentle, to maintain the trees' healthy as long as possible. **ALM** has developed the **USM mulcher** that combines two devices in one. Depending on the equipment of the working shaft, the user can mulch or stump. Allowing for a high area performance and gentle understorey care, it was developed primarily for fruit and wine growing.

Solutions for re-cultivation: A grub cutter may be used to cut back or create new short rotation stands, but mainly for the re-cultivation of the fields after the AFS is removed. It is important here that existing rootstocks are permanently destroyed to prevent new growth, either as attachable device to a tractor (*Fig. 7*) or a self-propelled heavy mulcher (*Fig. 8*).

Fig. 7. Re-cultivation of a poplar AFS strip with an attachable mulcher. Author: R. Hübner.

Fig. 8. Heavy land clearing equipment like the Prinoth RAPTOR 800 with 640 HP and 26 t weight is doing the job but may not be the first choice for AFS. Author: R. Hübner.

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Available machinery for fruit and nut harvesting and processing in agroforestry systems (DE)

Summary: This fact sheet presents some of the machinery for fruit and nut harvesting and processing in agroforestry systems currently available on the market.

Problem to solve: The presence of agricultural crops often limits the possibility to use traditional machineries used in conventional fruit production systems. This also applies to small-scale cereal crops harvesting technology, which is a speciality of AFS. There are hardly any suitable machines for this. When purchasing harvesting machines for AFS, it should be considered whether the machine is suitable for the existing tractors, whether it is easy to transport or whether a road licence is required, whether high or low stems are harvested and whether cider or dessert fruit is harvested.

Solutions with machineries for harvesting fruit, nuts and berries: For AFS, machines from professional fruit growing and viticulture are available in various sizes and designs. The [Obstblitz OB 40 from Feucht](#), for example, is suitable for the mechanised collection of apples, pears and nuts from orchards. This fruit-picking machine with electric drive collects between 700 and 1,500 kg per hour and works in high and damp grass, on uneven terrain and on slopes.

For nut **processing**, the company Feucht also offers the [WAL MAN hand driven nut-cracking machine](#) for walnuts and hazelnuts.

Fig. 9. The German manufacturer Krauss (SF) produces a range of medium sized fruit collectors. Author: R. Hübner.

Fig. 10. Manual fruit collector "Obstraupe" from Austria. Author: R. Hübner.

Fruit harvesters for small scale AFS with scattered tree-layout or traditional set-ups in systems like in orchard meadows, the [Obstraupe by OrganicTools](#) from Austria is a rather small-scale solution for fallen fruit collection. There are two models of these electric fruit harvesters available, either propelled by a powerful drill, which is available at every farm, or by an integrated e-motor and rechargeable battery (Fig. 10).

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Fig. 11. Large self-propelled fruit scraper and collector “Obstwiesel”. Author: R. Hübner.

Fig. 12. Self-propelled nut collector using vacuum technique for hazelnut. Author: R. Hübner.

Fruit scrapers or fruit blowers push or blow the fruit to the side, where they can then be picked up more easily and are therefore useful for row plantings in larger areas (Fig. 11). Similar machines with vacuum technology are available for nuts (Fig. 12), or with a bottom collection drum from French producer [AMB ROUSSET](#) (Fig. 14).

Trunk or tree shakers are suitable for harvesting apples, pears, stone fruits, almonds, walnuts and olives. The common shakers also differ in the clamping range, which limits the diameter of the trunks to be shaken, and in the shaking technique. The mechanical shaking technique works by pushing and pulling the trunk. Hydraulic shakers generally have a larger clamping range, a shorter shaking path and a higher shaking frequency. Most shakers are driven by the drive shaft of the tractor. Most models protect the bark from pressure damage with rubber belts. The [VHM trunk shaker from Feucht](#), for example, is another mechanical trunk shaker, while the [fruit shaker OS from Feucht](#) and is a 3-point cable shaker that is attached to the main branches of the crown with a steel cable – a bit more gentle to the stem. Both work for tree stem diameters of 5 to 25 cm.

Fig. 13. Hydraulic trunk shaker. Author: R. Hübner.

Fig. 14. French manufacturer AMB Rousset X16 harvester. Author: R. Hübner.

The Polish company [Jagoda](#), offers the [PESTKA trunk shaker](#) (for olives, plums, apples, cherries, and others) and the [GACEK tree shaker](#) (Sour cherry, Plum) which collects the shaken fruit in a

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kind of inverted umbrella, removes impurities with a fan and places the fruit in crates or pallet containers. It can be used to harvest 100 trees per hour for the PESTKA and 50-60 trees per hour using the GACEK, under optimal conditions. The JAREK 5, a berry harvesting machine developed by Jagoda, is an agroforestry-suitable machine. It features a modular design that allows for easy adaptation to the bushes and plantation conditions at every stage of use. Blackcurrants, Gooseberries, Saskatoon berries, and rose hips can be collected directly into crates or pallet containers. The company [AMMAC](#) in Wismar, Germany, offers large self-propelled or tractor-drawn harvesters for raspberries, blueberries and blackberries in the form of the various [OXBO models](#).

Solutions with machineries for small-scale cereal crops: The Italian agricultural machinery dealer [2M S.R.L.](#) from Povegliano Veronese imports small rice combine harvesters that were developed by the Japanese company [Kubota](#) decades ago. 2M S.R.L. has been importing these machines for 20 years and makes them available to interested parties for a reasonable price (around 7,000 €) on condition that they network with other users and develop their own support network.

Generally, however, no special machines are required, as new AFS should ideally be planned in such a way that the field strips between the rows of trees are at least one machine working width or a multiple of the working width.

Solutions with machineries for leafy biomass management. Leaf cutters or defoliators from the vineyard can be used for harvesting leaves as fodder, mulch or for other purposes. The Italian company [TECNOVICT](#), for example, offers various models that cut on one or both sides and at the top, as well as defoliators that harvest the leaves without damaging the fruit.

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Existing machineries for wood harvesting in agroforestry systems (DE)

Summary: This factsheet presents some of the machineries for timber harvesting in AFS currently available on the market.

Problem to solve: The presence of agricultural crops limits the possibility to use traditional machineries used in conventional forest or woodland for timber harvesting. Does the harvest have to be carried out by one person alone, or is a second person available to pick up the crop with a separate trailer? Pre-tensioning during felling can lead to injuries to the remaining root stock, which could increase the trees' susceptibility to disease in the long term.

Solution for machinery for log cuttings, logs, bundles or wood chips: Log cuttings and logs can be harvested manually with a chainsaw or fully mechanised with harvesters from the forestry sector. For harvesting bundles, feller-bunchers can be combined with bundle grippers e.g. the “Stemster” from the Danish company **Nordic Biomass**, according to Schweier and Becker [1] constructed for harvesting 3–4 year old willow SRC, or mowing collectors can be used or the [Woodcracker CL](#) for large stems (< 32 cm softwood) (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15. Woodcracker CL 260 with bundle. Author: A. Gernhardt.

Fig. 16. A telehandler as commonly used for transport on a farm. Author: T. Domin.

There are single-phase and two-phase harvesting systems for harvesting wood chips from short rotations. Single-phase systems are self-propelled chippers with premounted wood chipping units. Here, the wood chips are blown directly from the chipper into containers or trailers of tractors travelling in parallel. The most common systems are the **Claas Jaguar** with **HS-2 cutterbar**, the [New Holland](#) forage harvester with **130FB coppice header** and the **Krone BigX** with the **Hüttmann WoodCut** by German manufacturer Hüttmann GmbH from Soltau- Mittelstendorf. Cutting units from other manufacturers or custom designs have been developed specifically for the Claas Jaguar. For mounting on the tractor, there is, for example, the mounted mower chopper from **Schmidt GmbH in Uchte**. Another suitable device is the [Mower Chipper MH-130](#) by Kluge (Fig. 18). ATB developed this mower-chipper for a workable stem diameter of softwood (poplar, willow, black locust) of a diameter > 20 cm.

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The fully mechanised methods are suitable for large areas with slopes of less than 20 % and for stem diameters > 15 cm in cutting height (standard Claas Jaguar only > 7 cm). Single or double rows can be harvested at a maximum speed of 6 km/hour, the area output is between 0.6-1.6 hectares per hour. With the two-phase harvesting methods, the logs are harvested first and then chipped. This has the advantage that the logs can dry for several months after harvesting to a water content of 30-35 %, which improves the storability and calorific value of the wood chippings. Logs dry much better than wood chippings.

Fig. 17. Claas Jaguar with SRC device used for chopping softwood. Author: I. Frenzel.

Fig. 18. Mover-chipper harvesting a poplar stand at the first rotation. Author: C. Schulze.

Larger diameter trunks are felled with chainsaw, felling grapples or mowing collectors as with bundle harvesting (*Fig. 15*). However, the ratio of working time to yield due to the unloading of the harvested trees is less favourable with these harvesting methods, so they are more recommended for longer rotation periods of between 5 and 20 years. There are various sophisticated models of mobile chippers available for chipping, which can process all log diameters. The two-phase harvesting systems are thus particularly suitable for trunk diameters of more than 15 cm, for steep slopes with a gradient of more than 20 % or for small AFS of less than 1 ha and for woodchip production for own use. Some consideration should be given when purchasing mower-chopper attachments or chippers. Economically important factors can be the required tractor power, the transportability (weight) of the machine and the fuel consumption. Technically, a distinction is made between disc wheel chippers, drum chippers and auger chippers. As wood chips need to dry quickly and require a good storage for stability. This is achieved by clean cut edges and a low proportion of fines as well as little impurities or snow in the harvested material. Cleanly defined sizes increase the market value. With disc wheel chippers, the material feed can be about half the diameter of the discs; due to the flywheel mass of the discs, these chipping systems work with less drive power. The weight of the machine and especially that of the chopping discs should therefore be considered when purchasing; lighter chopping discs mean higher fuel consumption for the same chopping performance. Drum chippers can usually process logs with a thickness almost up to the entire drum diameter and are mainly suitable for high-performance contract use. Auger chippers work with an auger that increases in cross-section and automatically pulls the wood chips into the machine. The size of the wood chips cannot be varied. Auger chippers are usually simpler in design, have a low specific fuel consumption and are particularly suitable for smaller systems.

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5 Tools to deal with technical and labour-related challenges

Based on DIGITAF catalogue (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/>) a decision tree was built with the aim to help farmers and farm advisors in the selection of suitable tool to address their technical issues. After the decision tree, a description of the tools is presented.

Fig 19. Decision tree on technical tools

Description of tools, organized in alphabetical order:

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AgroBox

An agroecosystem dynamics sandbox for sustainable farming. The online tool allows to monitor pests, diseases, and weeds outbreaks comparing them in system with and without trees. The tools also allow the regulation of pesticide applications.

Link: <https://www.organicresearchcentre.com/resources/tools/agrobox-sandbox/>
DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/agrobox>

AgroforTreeAdvice

Decision Support System to help choose tree species/varieties/rootstocks for agroforestry systems. This is an aggregator of tree species selection tools. The online tool allows to insert the information regarding the field/site, and it constrains. Moreover, it allows to select the aim of the agroforestry system (i.e. animal, biomass, timber, etc.). Based on that it provides a list of suitable tree species that can be planted.

Link: <https://agroforestreetreeadvice.sk8.inrae.fr/>
DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/agroforestreetreeadvice>

Ammonia reduction calculator

Trees and woodlands have the potential to recapture ammonia emissions from animal housing units or areas where animals can roam free range under the canopy, with associated benefits for animal welfare and the environment. They can also be used to disperse emissions and reduce atmospheric nitrogen deposition reaching sensitive habitats. Existing, established woodland and the planting of new woodland (e.g. as farm tree shelterbelts) can therefore be used to reduce ammonia emissions and the environmental and social impacts associated. The UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH), and Forest Research Agency (FR) have developed a calculator and guidance for farmers, planners and tree planters, so they can maximize the benefits of planting tree shelterbelts for ammonia recapture. This includes information on several important aspects of planting, such as recommended planting distances and configurations, species which are better at ammonia capture and other aspects of design so that new planting for this purpose can optimize potential benefits and units located near existing woodland can be situated to capitalize on potential benefits.

Link: <https://farmtreestoair.ceh.ac.uk/ammonia-reduction-calculator>
DIGITAF catalogue link: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/ammonia_reduction_calculator

Betula

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This tool helps farmers & advisors to develop an agroforestry plan. Step by step, the user is guided through all aspects that need attention, from goal & species selection to planting & management issues. Betula is part of the overarching "Agroforestry Planner" set of digital tools for agroforestry in Flanders.

Link: <https://www.agroforestryvlaanderen.be/en/agroforestry-planner-2>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/betula>

BOOM

The tools allow to monitor and register the performances of nut trees and the operation conducted in the system.

Link: <https://www.notenteelt.com/shop/categorie/20-registratie-programma-bomen>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/boom>

De Juiste Boom op de Juiste Plek

A decision-making tool for tree and shrub species based on soil type and groundwater level.

Link: <https://kennisbank.agroforestrynetwerk.nl/de-juiste-boom-op-de-juiste-plek/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/de_juiste_boom_op_de_juiste_plek

DECIDOUS

Deciduous aims to help farmers & advisors interested in adding fruit trees in their established systems, to choose right fruit species, rootstock and cultivar according to their local soil/climate/time constraints. The tool allows to insert the information of your plot (i.e. possibility of irrigation, soil depth, water retention, level of calcium) and desired tree characteristics (i.e. tree height). Additionally, it is possible to select the time availability on your farm and which months. Once inserted the app present a list of options with the relative score.

Link: <https://www.grab.fr/deciduous-page-principale/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/deciduous>

DEXiAF

DEXiAF is a free software tool co-developed by INRAE, GRAB, and UniLaSalle Beauvais, designed for field actors and trainers to: (i) Finalize your agroforestry system prototype using a comprehens-

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ive checklist; (ii) Evaluate your agroforestry system before planting, on the three pillars of sustainability in each context.

Link: <https://means.inrae.fr/eng/emc-tools/dexiaf>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/dexiaf>

e-planner

E-Planner is a free tool developed by UKCEH to help farmers and other land managers identify the most suitable places for different environmental management actions via easy to use, interactive maps.

Link: <https://e-planner.ceh.ac.uk/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/eplanner>

Ecological Site Classification (ESC)

Ecological Site Classification is a web-based decision support system to help forest managers and planners select tree species that are ecologically suited to sites, instead of selecting a species and trying to modify the site to suit. ESC applies the Ecological Site Classification methodology and provides a user-friendly way of working out options for tree species and native woodland communities on individual sites. Site information required Basic site information is provided simply by entering a grid reference, this provides climatic data and default coarse resolution soil quality information. If additional detailed soil information and plant indicator species are available, a more precise determination of site quality, and a better estimate of species suitability and yield is provided by ESC. If more information is known about a site (e.g. rooting depth, soil texture and stoniness) a more precise estimate of the soil wetness can be made. If lithology is known this is combined with soil type to provide a more precise estimate of soil fertility. Humus form can give even more precision, but the best estimate of soil fertility is gained from a knowledge of the plants on the site. ESC uses two models to assess fertility using 132 indicator plants that commonly occur in woodlands, grasslands and heathlands. The field survey pack (see Downloads page); is available to provide help with soil and plant identification and with methods for estimating soil texture and stoniness. The site information is linked to ESC suitability models for 20 of the 25 NVC woodland communities (W1-W20) and 60 species of tree using a 'fuzzy membership function' approach. Site yield projections are also provided by the ESC decision support system. The fuzzy membership function describes the degree of suitability of the species or woodland community to each ESC site factor. ESC 3 incorporates future climate change projections for the UKCIP02 low and high emissions scenarios for 2050 and 2080, to allow users to incorporate future suitability into planting decisions. The high emissions scenarios are based on the IPCC A1Fi SRES scenario and should give a better indication of the extreme values of AT and MD that are likely to affect forests and woodlands in the future. Future climate scenarios ESC 3 incorporates future climate change projections for the UKCIP02 low and high emissions scenarios for 2050 and 2080, to allow users to incorporate future suitability into planting decisions. User friendly system ESC includes a set of cue cards that leads the user through the site analysis and the species and woodland community suitability assessment. It includes an on-line help

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system containing background information. Source: <https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/fthr/ecological-site-classification/about-esc/>

Link: <https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/tools-and-resources/fthr/ecological-site-classification/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/ecological_site_classification_esc

GoÖko – Heckenmanager (Hedgerow Manager)

The GoÖko Hedgerow Manager (German: *Heckenmanager*) is a decision-support tool for the management and planning of hedges in agricultural areas, taking sustainability aspects into account. In addition to a step-by-step guide, the application is linked to a separate woody plant database. The hedge manager can be used free of charge on the DeFAF website. For the hedgerow ecosystem services assessment, a hedgerow structure index was developed based on literature data. It was proposed for the evaluation of hedgerow quality in relation to agrobiodiversity. This index considers the following characteristics of hedgerows structural diversity that are important for biodiversity: i) hedgerow width, ii) hedgerow structure, iii) hedgerow height, iv) tree diameter, v) species diversity, vi) food source, vii) hedgerow continuity and viii) hedgerow density. In general, the higher the structural diversity of hedgerows the higher their potential value as a habitat and food source for a variety of species. Once the target area has been selected, hedges can be managed, transformed or entirely replanted. A feature that can be used for planning diverse agroforestry systems. The ecosystem services are evaluated in relation to the status quo. Finally, a pdf is generated that covers all previously defined planning aspects, including a planting plan and order lists for obtaining quotations, handing in to the authorities or request for funding.

The hedgerow manager was developed between 2019 and 2021. The final report can be accessed here: [link to the report](#)

Link: <https://hecken-landschaft.de/entscheidungshilfe>

DIGITAF catalogue link: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/goko_heckenmanager_hedgerow_manager

i-Tree Design

This tool helps you estimate individual tree benefits in terms of carbon dioxide, air pollution, storm-water impacts and energy savings. How to use it: (i) plot a tree or planting location on a map, (ii) select its species, (iii) enter trunk diameter or circumference, and (iv) select the general condition of the tree. If you take the additional step of sketching the outline of a nearby house, you can see how your trees impact building energy use. i-Tree Design estimates tree benefits for the current year and up to 99 years in the future. Total benefits to date based on estimated tree age are also provided. Multiple trees and buildings can be modelled.

Link: <https://design.itreetools.org/>

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DIGITAF catalogue link: -

i-Tree Planting

Easily estimate the long-term environmental benefits from a tree planting project in terms of carbon dioxide, air pollution, stormwater impacts, energy savings, and canopy cover. How to use it: (i) *enter groups of trees with the following information*: tree species; size of trees at planting, condition of the trees; the number of trees in the group; project lifetime years. (ii) *optionally, enter more values to fine tune your estimates*: distance and direction to the nearest building, estimated mortality of the trees over the project lifetime, specific greenhouse gas values for your region, tree benefit estimates are calculated in amounts and dollar values (carbon dioxide sequestered, carbon dioxide avoided due to reduction in building energy use, energy conserved, air pollutants captured and avoided, storm-water filtered, tree total biomass, canopy cover).

Link: <https://planting.itreetools.org/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: -

i-Tree Species

Select tree species for planting projects based on their potential benefits and geographic region. How to use it: choose your planting location, then select and rank the importance from 0 to 10 of each desired tree benefit. Species selections will be based on three types of information: (i) hardiness – as determined by state and city, (ii) mature height – user specified minimum and maximum heights, (iii) environmental factors – ranked from 0 to 10: carbon storage, air pollution removal, storm water impacts, building energy conservation, pollen allergenicity, and reductions in air temperature, ultraviolet radiation, and wind. A ranked list will be created with recommended species suited for local use that maximize tree benefits. It will be based on a combination of hardiness, mature height, and desired, potential benefits. The results can be used as a starting point and adjusted to meet local and cultural needs and limitations. To learn more about the methodology, review the [Help](#) documentation.

Link: <https://species.itreetools.org/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: -

Land App

A brand-new free digital agroforestry designer toolkit is being launched by cloud-based mapping software company Land App and partners. Aimed at farmers, estate managers and land agents across the UK, Land App's ground-breaking new Agroforestry Designer Toolkit aims to platform agroforestry – the intentional integration of trees into farms – and its many benefits to farmers, their livestock and nature.

Link: <https://thelandapp.com/>

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DIGITAF catalogue link: https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/land_app

MIMOSA

The "Agroforestry Planner", developed by the partners of Agroforestry Flanders, is a digital platform that aims to support farmers, advisors, and (agroforestry) experts by offering a variety of decision-support tools. One of the tools included in the Agroforestry Planner is the MIMOSA tool. This interactive calculation tool gives the user targeted advice for the cost-efficient harvesting of walnuts and hazelnuts. The tool thereto uses a set of site-specific (e.g. area, number of trees, wages, ...) and fixed parameters (working width, harvesting speed, fuel consumption, purchase price, depreciation period and machine loading capacity). Based on these parameters the cost price of harvesting the nut plantation using different types of machinery is calculated. The overall objective of MIMOSA is to support the user in making the right choices considering scale and farm specific preferences. By June 2026, an update of this tool (including new devices and price updates) and an English version are foreseen.

Link: <https://bdbnet.bdb.be/pls/apex/f?p=147:10>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/mimosa>

RegenWorks

RegenWorks is a GIS-based software for agroforestry design that provide realistic 3D visualization. It is al a hyperlocal GIS-based Agroforestry System Adaptation.

Link: <https://regenfarmer.com/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: -

Sectomentor

Sectormentor for Trees helps you manage the health of your trees, and the soils beneath them. It allows to farm mapping and to record farm data (i.e. soil tests, daily observations, photos).

Link: <https://tech.vidacycle.com/sectormentor-for-trees-fruits/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: -

ShadeTreeAdvice

ShadeTreeAdvice is an online decision-support tool designed to assist farmers in selecting suitable shade tree species for their farms. The tool's core is a method to gather and consolidate the local ecological knowledge of farmers who are already managing agroforestry systems. This process leads to a database of tree species and their effectiveness in providing various local services (e.g.,

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soil fertility, weather protection, and supplemental revenue). Farmers seeking to introduce trees onto their farms can specify the services they prioritize, and the tool will rank tree species that offer the best trade-offs, based on the knowledge shared by other local farmers. To date, ShadeTreeAdvice supports tree species selection for coffee and cocoa farms in over 10 locations across the tropical belt.

Link: <https://www.shadetreeadvice.org/>

DIGITAF catalogue link: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools/tool/shadetreeadvice>

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6 Tools to deal with administrative issues

Within this section, we present suggestions to address the administrative issues appearing as problematic to farmers according to the initial survey conducted within DigitAF Living Labs (DigitAF Deliverable [2.1](#) (Tranchina et al 2024)). Since administrative issues are linked to the country-specific laws and regulations, these solutions are presented country by country, for Belgium, Italy and Germany.

Administrative barriers and challenges to the establishment and continuation of agroforestry in Belgium

In Belgium, more specifically in the region of Flanders, the three administrative issues rated with the highest grade in the survey were: (i) “*Issues related to land ownership*”, (ii) “*Issues related to permits for removing trees*”, (iii) “*Administrative burden when implementing AF systems*” (Table 3). The issues of access to land and land ownership are of uttermost importance and goes beyond but certainly also has an impact on agroforestry practices. This topic receives quite some attention within ILVO research and policy advice, as is shown in [this publication](#). However, in this deliverable we focus on the other issues more directly related to agroforestry.

A summary of administrative issues in Flanders, and how they are faced

The reasons for promoting agroforestry within the policy framework of the EU and thus Flanders are convincing and supported by robust scientific evidence. Agroforestry supports multiple objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), including food security, environmental protection, climate action and rural development. Agroforestry systems also align with the Farm to Fork strategy, which aims to create a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system.

In Flanders, there is also a very direct connection to a number of policy frameworks, including the [Flemish Energy and Climate Plan](#) (VEKP), the (draft) LULUCF action plan and the [Go4Food Food Deal](#) (deal Agroecology). Also the new [Flemish Governmental Agreement 2024-2029](#) offers many opportunities

In recent years a number of important steps towards this have already been taken in Flanders: first to explicitly recognize agroforestry in legislation, and second to develop [financial incentives](#) through subsidies for planting (since 2011), maintenance (since 2023) and recently also guidance (since 2025). The number of expert consultants in agroforestry and food forestry is gradually growing, and opportunities are created for farm advisors to train in agroforestry. Besides the Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries, the [Consortium Agroforestry Flanders](#) is playing a crucial role here.

Nevertheless, as in most European member states, there is a very significant underspending of the budget for agroforestry ([EURAF policy briefing #69](#)). Since the introduction of the agroforestry planting subsidy in Flanders in 2011, only 300 ha of agroforestry were installed with the help of this subsidy. Moreover, we are currently observing a downward trend in the number of applications and the associated acreage. The recently tightened rules to meet the criterium of “active farmer” certainly play a role here, but even more, agroforestry entrepreneurs often face a substantial load of laws and regulations with many administrative rules and obligations, in which it is difficult to find their way. Moreover, regulations at the various levels are not always coherent. In particular the fact that agroforestry pioneers are often venturing into unexplored territory, means that existing regulations and

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control systems are insufficiently adapted to new developments and therefore counterproductive to innovation and experimentation.

Given the still often experimental nature of agroforestry, it is somewhat logical that not all the rules of the game in terms of legislation, policy and administrative procedures are yet fully in place nor equally clear to all stakeholders. However, we observe several remaining uncertainties, ambiguities, contradictions and barriers around legislation and subsidy conditions, but particularly also the administrative burden associated with it. These issues negatively affect the choice to start with agroforestry. A significant proportion of farmers who applied for the agroforestry subsidy in the period 2011-2023 reported a feeling of disappointment or dissatisfaction regarding the application procedure, control and/or (partial) rejection of subsidy applications (Vanpoucke 2024 and personal communication).

Frequently reported administrative issues are:

- Time lag between initial investment by the farmer and subsidy payment (often up to 2 years).
- Rigid regulatory framework, missing a holistic, systemic evaluation considering bigger farm context and reality.
- Non-uniform interpretation of rules/conditions during initial approval of subsidy requests as well as during terrain control (e.g. tree density, tree and tree strip maintenance, which trees considered part of the AF system and which not, ...).
- Approach of terrain controls, which often happens unannounced and in absence of the farmer.

We intend to reverse that trend through collaboration with all stakeholders.

A crucial first step is to take this complex set of laws, regulations and subsidy policy, and to create an overview and improve clarity. At this moment, our foremost “tool” therefore also consists of a set of factsheets providing insight in regulations, subsidy options and administrative procedures. These factsheets can be found (in Dutch) on the Agroforestry Knowledge Hub for Flanders ([here](#)). On top of that, ILVO as coordinator of the Consortium Agroforestry Flanders also takes up the role of interest representative for practitioners in continuous interaction with the administrations and policy makers.

Above all, a solution-oriented approach by the administrative instances, with a focus on the ultimate (policy) objectives, with room for dialogue and based on cooperation and trust, would make a very meaningful difference. Farmers are strongly demanding a solution-oriented approach rather than a controlling one, both in the agroforestry context and in farming in general.

In addition, the extent to which agroforestry can contribute to certain larger policy objectives (such as climate change adaptation and water management, for example) is not sufficiently clear to many policy actors, or the response to that potential is very fragmented. Strengthening policy actors' affinity with exactly what agroforestry is about, is imperative. So does mutual coordination between policy actors from various departments, services, domains and levels.

Having said that, the willingness to listen is quite big from the side of the Flemish administration services. There is a noticeable will to support agroforestry for the better. But at present, the climate and ecosystem services that an agroforestry system can provide are insufficiently recognized. This leads to a vicious circle: a measure that is too small can hardly justify a considerable (time) investment by policy actors, but precisely because of this, the measure is also given insufficient opportunity for further development.

In summary, there is a clear need for an approach within the administrations where different agencies recognize agroforestry and the added value of this form of agriculture, and work together to

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develop a unified regulatory framework (i.e. a “policy plan for agroforestry”), considering the specific characteristics and assets of this system.

To pursue this future vision in which Flemish policy and administrative actors support the scale-up of successful and effective agroforestry systems, the most overarching need is to bring together actors from different policy areas and levels in an active and coordinated manner to work on a coherent plan of action for the abovementioned challenges and vision. This can take shape in many ways and grow step by step, but it is important (1) that a clear vision, mission and ambition are put forward and (2) that the initiative comes from the interested policy actors themselves, albeit in close cooperation with the *Consortium Agroforestry Vlaanderen*. Therefore, in the framework of DigitAF, ILVO proposed a “policy pathway” within the “[Roadmap towards an enabling environment for agroforestry in Flanders](#)” document. At this moment (status May 2025), the Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries has picked up this suggestion and is taking the first steps to the development of such a ‘working group’.

Currently available tools most directly of interest for administrations and policy actors within this context, are (1) the EU and Flemish [agroforestry map](#), and (2) the Carbon Agroforestry Tool “CARAT”, supporting also these actors in developing carbon policies as well as in quantifying the impact of tree related measures (e.g. LULUCF). In the near future, the further development of an agroforestry design tool might be an effective means not only to develop an AF plan but could also support follow-up monitoring and terrain control.

Administrative barriers and challenges to the establishment and continuation of agroforestry in Italy

In Italy the three administrative issues rated with the highest grade were: (i) “Entity of support of Common Agricultural Policy measures”, (ii) “Issues related to permits for removing trees”, (iii) “Issues related to permits for agroforestry-related infrastructure” (Table 3).

In the Tuscany Region, tree removal is regulated by the *Regolamento Forestale della Toscana* (Reg. No. 48/R, 2003) ([Reg. No. 48/R, 2003](#)). It outlines when forest conversion is allowed, such as for hydrogeological protection, disease control in chestnut orchards, phytosanitary reasons, or research, always with prior technical approval.

For tree plantations and isolated trees on agricultural land (outside forest), specific thresholds apply (e.g., trunk diameter and species, or using of orthophotos). Permits or notifications are often required depending on the intervention. Protection also applies to hedgerows, rows, and small tree groups, which may only be pruned or cut under specific conditions and with authorization if their extent is reduced. Cutting is generally allowed only for declining or dangerous trees, phytosanitary needs, land management, or justified farm operations. All interventions are subject to pest control regulations.

Moreover, infrastructure essential for agroforestry systems, such as fencing, irrigation tanks, tool or livestock shelters, often encounters significant regulatory hurdles in Italy. These structures are crucial for integrated land management but are frequently subject to: (i) Landscape protection con-

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straints, especially in protected areas, and hydrogeological or urban planning restrictions, which vary by region.

The regulatory framework is fragmented at the local level, generating uncertainty and delays for farmers.

According to Tranchina et al. (2024), administrative burden is one of the main perceived barriers to agroforestry adoption, alongside initial investment costs and lack of technical support. Bureaucratic complexity also limits the implementation of new technologies and infrastructure, hindering the effectiveness and long-term sustainability of agroforestry initiatives.

Lastly, the support provided by the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for agroforestry in Italy remains limited, fragmented, and often unclear. While some Regions have included agroforestry in their Rural Development Plans (RDPs), measures are inconsistently applied, and eligibility criteria are not well adapted to the complexity of agroforestry systems. Farmers and advisors report difficulties accessing funds and navigating bureaucratic procedures, especially when agroforestry practices do not neatly fit within predefined CAP categories. This lack of coherent, dedicated support discourages broader adoption and undermines the potential of agroforestry to deliver multiple ecosystem services and climate resilience.

Policy Recommendations for the Implementation of Agroforestry in Italy

The large-scale adoption of agroforestry in Italy urgently requires a more coherent and coordinated political and regulatory framework. Currently, the measures and sub-measures provided in the second pillar (RDP) of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) aimed at supporting agroforestry systems are characterized by significant territorial heterogeneity: they not only vary considerably among Regions but are often not activated at all, leaving entire areas uncovered and discouraging farmers interested in investing in these practices.

Although the new National Strategic Plan (PSP) for the CAP 2023–2027 recognizes agroforestry as a key practice for the ecological transition of agriculture, the lack of nationally shared guidelines and effective central coordination continues to hinder its widespread adoption. A concrete commitment is therefore needed from the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry (MASAF) and the Regions to harmonize access procedures, eligibility criteria, and funding priorities, taking into account the diversity of Italy's agroecological systems.

Currently, both the National Rural Network (RRN) managed by CREA and the Italian Agroforestry Association (AIAF) are active in promoting these systems, but results remain limited. The main causes lie in widespread lack of knowledge and insufficient dissemination and democratization of the concept of agroforestry, especially among regional officials and farmers' associations.

At the regional level, even when Rural Development Program (RDP) measures are activated, the division between sub-measures for establishment and maintenance does not foster clarity nor encourage farmers to push their associations to request activation of such measures in coordination tables.

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Moreover, the transfer of innovation supporting the transformation of agricultural systems through agroforestry has not been fully exploited. Cooperation and innovation measures (former sub-measures 16.1 and 16.2) and EIP-AGRI Operational Groups have never been jointly activated with investment measures for farms, preventing the development of medium- to long-term multidisciplinary projects that could ensure both innovation transfer and financial support to farmers.

Therefore, it is recommended to: (i) increase efforts in the dissemination and communication of agroforestry, its benefits, and limitations at the national level, involving key stakeholders of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) to facilitate the transition, (ii) standardize specific measures within the RSF to guarantee support both for initial investments and for ongoing maintenance for farmers wishing to develop agroforestry systems, and (iii) harmonize regional instruments to accelerate agroforestry adoption through the creation of multi-measure medium-long term project (e.g., 4 years), including innovation and investments measures and activities, to ensure long-lasting collaboration among agricultural stakeholders, supply chains actors, and knowledge providers (e.g., universities and research centres).

Only through a coordinated and systemic approach will it be possible to fully unlock the potential of agroforestry for sustainable and resilient agriculture in Italy.

Barriers and challenges to the establishment and continuation of agroforestry in Germany

Challenges and implementation difficulties expressed by various agroforestry stakeholders from Germany were identified through the survey. These are supplemented with current findings from the literature. In Germany, the three administrative issues that received the highest ratings were:

- (i) *“Administrative burden when implementing AF systems”*,
- (ii) *“Issues related to permits for removing trees”*,
- (iii) *“Issues related to permits for agroforestry-related infrastructure”*.

Eco-schemes (ES) as an instrument of the “Green Architecture” of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) have been newly introduced. Since 2023, German farms have been able to receive support for the management of AFS from the Pillar I via ES #3 “Maintaining agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland”. From an initial funding rate of 60 € per hectare of wooded area in 2024 to 200 € in 2025, further adjustments are planned to reduce the bureaucracy of ES #3. From 2026 on, ES #3 is to be increased to 600 € per hectare per the decision of the Agricultural Ministers' Conference (AMK) [2].

Accompanying investment support, which is intended to serve as a basis for the later maintaining of the AFS, is only offered in a few German federal states encompassed by major bureaucratic and regulatory hurdles. Support for advice on agroforestry issues is the third support instrument offered in three German federal states.

Administrative burden when implementing AFS

Feedback on both, the ES #3 and the lack/non-existence of investment support has not been very positive. Criticism is levelled at the lack of harmonisation between agroforestry as an agricultural

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use under agricultural law on the one hand and nature conservation law on the other. This prevents planning security and self-determination for farmers. In addition, the political trust of AFS supporters is low due to political decision-making processes at regional and national levels, which are perceived as opaque and untrustworthy.

Bureaucratic processes are considered overly cumbersome for farmers and the responsible authorities. The eligibility criteria for ES #3 and – if available – tightly bound investment measures are largely considered disproportionate and restrictive, as they offer farmers little to no flexibility in implementing a wide range of AFS. Furthermore, they are not suited to agricultural practices and are not sufficiently geared towards ecological benefits. The low funding amounts for both measures are insufficient to compensate for the implementation and management costs and the positive environmental benefits achieved, or to compensate for the achievement of the CAP Strategic Plan objectives. The short funding periods for ES impair the planning security of farms and are therefore ineffective in terms of achieving environmental and climate benefits [3].

In addition to existing competition from more attractively subsidised agri-environmental schemes (AES) and, in terms of effort, significantly more attractively subsidised eco-schemes, there are also difficult-to-overcome restrictions under subsidy law. In two federal states, ES #3 is not permitted on grassland and in nine federal states on permanent crops. In addition, each German federal state has specific “combination tables” to avoid potential double funding with AES. Combination with ES #1 (flower strips) or the cultivation of different crops between the woody strips is prohibited nationwide.

Issues related to permits for removing trees

With recognition in subsidy law under GAPDZV §4, the legal situation of AFS in Germany has improved significantly; however, uncertainties remain in the application of specialist law, particularly in nature conservation law [3, 4].

One concern expressed by some farmers regarding the legal certainty of AFS, is the fear that agroforestry areas are being reclassified as forest, which would lead to restrictions on subsequent agricultural use and immediate financial losses [5]. The bureaucratic effort involved deters participation: farmers stated that they would need their ‘own administrative team just for the agroforestry-paperwork’. Confusing eligibility criteria in agroforestry support programmes and frequent policy changes in general, which create uncertainty about long-term support, were also mentioned [5].

Solutions to make administrative procedures more flexible and simplify the application process

Barriers to implementation stem from contradictory interpretations of subsidy law and statutory law in the field of environment and agriculture at the regional/local level. Decision-making and assessments by authorities should be evaluated based on sound technical expertise regarding the environmental impacts. Scientific studies show predominantly positive effects. To this end, the terms “agroforestry” and “agroforestry systems” should be added or adapted in the relevant administrative guidelines issued by the higher authorities at the state level.

Where possible, a regulation should be drawn up to oblige lower authorities to support the establishment of AFS wherever possible and to remove bureaucratic obstacles. Excluding large areas from protected areas, such as Landscape Protected Areas, also prevents positive effects from being achieved with agroforestry cultivation methods in these regions.

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The integration of the term ‘agroforestry’ into the German Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG) would mean recognising agroforestry as an agricultural use and extending the agricultural privilege to AFS. AFS would then no longer be fundamentally questioned regarding the character of a negative intervention. Under agricultural law, AFS are already defined as agricultural activities ([6] § 3). Their establishment does not result in a change in land use, as the agricultural area remains arable land, permanent crops or permanent grassland ([6] § 4).

Solutions to improve the agroforestry-related infrastructure, strengthen the support for advisory services and education

The market situation for agroforestry products should be strengthened. Policy incentives should promote the use of agricultural products from climate-friendly farming methods, such as AFS or paludiculture. Publicly funded projects can provide incentives and at the same time generate regional value added at the same time. In the construction sector, for example, emissions could be reduced if greater use were made of renewable raw materials (wood [explicitly from AFS] instead of cement and steel, etc.). This type of construction using certified building materials with emission avoidance indicators could, for example, be promoted through tax incentives. The use of agroforestry products for energy purposes could also be strengthened. The EEG (German Renewable Energy Sources Act) could be used here, for example, to provide greater support for energy generation plants that use wood from AFS, etc.

Standards covering everything from cultivation, processing and recycling to final use, such as the DIN-SPEC (DIN-specification) [7] currently under development, provide a basis for certified carbon removal through the use of regional, bio-based and recyclable raw materials.

Enable nationwide promotion of advisory services. Promoting initial and ongoing (nature conservation) planning and advice would ensure comprehensive and thematically focused advisory services and enable broader implementation with an open outcome. Examples at the state level in the federal states of Brandenburg [8] and Baden-Württemberg show promising approaches. In addition, promoting counselling would also enhance the value of the qualification for existing advisors.

Nationwide promotion of training and further education is needed. Suitable formats for training and further education should be strengthened. This includes further training for employees in public authorities and offices, and implementation in training for green professions.

WP2 – Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

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